

Effect of Vitamins on Protease and Lipase Production in Seed-Borne Fungi of Soybean

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Abstract:

During the process of biodeterioration, seed mycoflora produce enzymes to degrade protein, carbohydrate and oil. These enzymes called as hydrolytic enzymes. The enzymes which degrade proteins are called protease and enzymes which degrade oil are lipase.

It is observed that total thirty species of fungi were isolated from ten varieties of Soybean. It is also observed that different Oils such as castor on protease production is stimulatory except *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. niger*. Clove inhibited most of the fungi except *Curvularia lunata*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma viride*. It produced no protease by *A. niger* and *Trichoderma viride*. Neem only inhibits the fungi like *A. alternata*, *A. flavus* and *A. niger*.

Keywords: Vitamins, Protease, Lipase, Fungi.

Introduction:

Seed plays a vital role for the production of healthy crop. These seeds are also responsible for disease transmission. This takes place either in the field or in ill storage condition. Neergard(1977) reported that in the presence of seed-borne pathogens, several types of abnormalities like reduction in seed size, seed rotting, discoloration of seeds, seed necrosis, loss in germ inability, toxification and other physiological disorders. According to Sandikar (1990) the species of *fusarium* are found to be significantly destructive and responsible to cause harmful effect on seed health resulting in to seed deterioration and poisoning of seeds. During the process of biodeterioration, fungi produce enzymes to degrade proteins, carbohydrates and oil. Sharma and Satyanarayana (1980) studied production of protease by some fungi such as *Helminthosporium*, *Glomerella cingulata*, *Curvularia geniculata*, *Alternaria pelandui*.

Umatale(1995), Charya and Reddy (1982) also studied on lipase production in

certain oil seeds. Umatale found *Aspergillusflavus*, *A.helianthi*, *Macrophominaphasiolina* and *Rhizopus nigricans* are more active to produce lipase.

Materials And Methods:

Collection of Samples and Detection of Seed Mycoflora:

For the collection of seed samples, the method described by Neergaard (1973) has been adopted. Accordingly, from fields, store houses market places and seed companies. A composite sample of each variety was prepared by mixing the individual samples together. The seed mycoflora was isolated by using slanted moist blotter paper method (SMB) and agar plate method (APM) as recommended by International seed testing association (ISTA 1966) ,De Tempe (1970) ,Neergaard (1973) and Agarwal (1976) .

Identification of seed borne fungi:

The fungi occurring on each and every seed in the plates were identified preliminary on

the basis of sporulation characters like sexual or asexual spores with the help of stereoscopic binocular microscope. The identification and further confirmation of seed-borne fungi was made by preparing slides of the fungal growth and observing them under compound microscope. The identification was made with the help of manuals as per Nelson, et.al. (1983), Singh, et.al.(1991), Mukadam D.S.(1997) and Mukadam et.al. (2006).

I) Production of Protease:

Production of protease(s) was made by growing the fungi on liquid medium containing glucose 10g, gelatin 10g, dipotassium hydrogen phosphate 1.0g, $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ -500mg and distilled water-1000ml. pH of the medium was adjusted at 5.5. Twenty-five ml of medium was poured in 100ml Erlenmeyer conical flasks and autoclaved at 15 lbs pressure for 20 minutes. The flasks on cooling were inoculated separately with 10ml standard spore/mycelial suspension of test fungi prepared from 7 days old cultures grown on PDA slants. The flasks were incubated for 6 days at $25 \pm 1^\circ C$ with diurnal periodicity of light. On 7th day, flasks were harvested by filtering the contents through Whatman's filter No.1. The filtrates were collected in the pre-sterilised bottles and termed as crude enzyme preparation.

Assay Method (cup-plate method)

Determination of protease(s) activity was done with the help of cup-plate method, adopted by Hislop *et. al.*, (1982) and Rajamani (1990). A basal medium was prepared by adding 2% (w/v) agar and one percent (w/v) gelatin. pH of the medium was adjusted at 5.6 with Mellavaine's buffer. Then it was sterilized at 15 lbs pressure for 15 minutes. About 15 ml of the medium was poured in presterilized petriplates under aseptic condition. On solidification 6mm diameter cups/cavities were made in the centre of each of the agar plate with a sterilized cork borer (No.4).

The cups/cavities were filled carefully with about 0.5ml of culture filtrate (crude enzyme preparation). The plates were incubated at $25^\circ C$ for 24 hours. Then the plates were flooded with 15 percent mercuric chloride in 7N HCl. After 10 minutes of standing, a clear transparent zone indicated the hydrolysis of gelating by extracellular proteolytic enzymes, whereas the rest of the region of the petriplates become opaque due to the coagulation (protein) by mercuric chloride. Diameter of the clear zone was used as measure (mm) of protease activity, while non appearance of clear zone considered absence of protease (s) in the culture filtrates.

II) Production of Lipase:

Lipase activity was studied by growing the fungi on liquid medium at pH5.6 containing oil-10g, KNO_3 -2.5g, KH_2PO_4 -1.0g, $MgSO_2$ – 0.5g and distilled water 1000ml. 25ml of the medium was poured in 100ml conical flasks and autoclaved at 15 lbs pressure for 30 minutes, then on cooling the flasks were inoculated separately with 1.0ml spore suspension of the fungi which were incubated for 6 days at $25 \pm 1^\circ C$ with diurnal periodicity of light. On 7th day of the flasks were harvested by filtering the contents through Whatman filter paper no.1. The filtrates were collected in presterilized culture filtrate bottles and termed as crude lipase.

Assay Method (Cup-plate method):

Determination of lipase activity was done with the help of cup-plate method. The medium contains Difco peptone-10g, NaCl-5g, $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ -1.0g, agar 2 percent and 10ml lipid substrate serbitan mono laurate (Tween-20) (Pre-sterilized) was added to it. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 6.00. The medium was poured in each Petri plate. On solidifying the medium with the help of a cork borer (No.4) was made in the centre and was filled with 0.1ml culture filtrate. The plates were incubated at $28^\circ C$. After 24

hours, a clear circular zone was measured (mm) as lipase activity. Similar procedure was followed for the culture filtrate in the central cavity instead of the active enzymes.

Result And Discussion:

Vitamins are very important in many vital activities of fungi. Therefore five commonly used vitamins at 100ppm concentration were used in protease and lipase production. The results are shown in table.

Except pyridoxine in case of *Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus flavus* almost all the

sources of vitamins stimulates the protease activity by all ten fungal species.

In case of lipase activity all sources of vitamins stimulates production of lipase by *A. alternata* while other nine fungi inhibited by all sources of vitamins. There is no activity of lipase was seen in *Fusarium oxysporum* by vitamin A and riboflavin while *Spicaria violecia* also produce no lipase with ascorbic acid vitamin A, Thiamin Riboflavin and pyridoxine. Same results are seen in *Trichoderma viride* except with Ascorbic acid.

Table: Effect of Vitamins on protease and lipase production in seed-borne fungi.

Vitamins	Fungi									
	Activity Zone (mm)									
100ppm conc.	Aal	Asf	Asn	Asg	Asu	Cul	Fur	Fuo	Spv	Triv
Protease Production										
Ascrbic acid	20	20	22	16	20	15	23	17	20	18
Vitamin A	20	22	20	16	19	15	22	16	19	15
Thiamin	24	27	30	23	26	22	26	18	24	19
Riboflavin	21	24	22	20	21	21	24	16	20	18
Pyridoxin	11	11	18	13	14	13	18	18	14	14
Control	18	20	18	16	12	13	18	12	11	11
Lipase Production										
Ascorbic acid	30	12	14	12	14	12	13	13	0	11
Vitamin A	33	12	18	15	17	11	13	0	0	0
Thiamin	30	14	15	19	18	12	15	13	0	0
Riboflavin	31	13	15	16	13	12	20	0	0	0
pyridoxin	28	12	14	13	15	11	15	11	0	0
Control	27	23	24	30	25	24	35	17	18	12
Aal – <i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Fuo – <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>									
Asf – <i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Spv – <i>Spicaria violecia</i>									
Asn – <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Triv – <i>Trichoderma viride</i>									
Asg – <i>Aspergillus glaucus</i>										
Asu – <i>Aspergillus ustus</i>										
Cul – <i>Curvularia lunata</i>										
Fur – <i>Fusarium roseum</i>										

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